

The Hypothesis of an Asymmetric Universe

Recently, I came across an interesting hypothesis that claims that the laws of physics about 10 billion light-years from us are the same as in our galaxy (the Milky Way). But this hypothesis is unproven and it's hard to verify or disprove it.

What if I present my own hypothesis to you in simple terms, one that is impossible not to accept?

My hypothesis is this:

The entire universe cannot be symmetric, due to the asymmetry of the space surrounding us.

It sounds dumb, and too easy, I don't argue. But I'll try to explain.

If you think about it more simply, a vivid example of asymmetry within the framework of physical laws is the Moon. On Earth, the law of gravity works, preventing us from floating away after a jump. On the Moon, we soar upwards due to the violation of this gravity. In space, it's completely absent.

Tell me that the hypothesis itself means the laws of the planet? I gave the example of the Moon. Different soil, different physical laws, different climate.

Tell me that it means the physical laws of Earth and our entire galaxy? And here you are also wrong.

Symmetry is when, for example, a mug half-filled with water stands on a perfectly level table, with precise proportions, with exact symmetry, and next to it is another mug, with the same pattern and shape, with the same water, and filled halfway with atomic precision.

Not enough examples, I understand. But what if we dig deeper?

Imagine an ideal room of mirrors, on the floor, around you, above you, but without any gaps connecting them. Someone might say, so what? But just imagine it. The brain will be disoriented, but will soon get used to it.

Let's make it more interesting. Let's place perfectly symmetric objects exactly opposite each other. Let's hang spheres, perfect in size (the image of planets), and live there for 2 weeks. There's no need to leave the room, on the condition that your biological needs are disabled (toilet, food).

Your brain will not thank you, and after about 5 days, it will go crazy from the perfect space and boredom.

This is most likely why planets, stars, quasars, black holes, meteorites, and everything else are not alike in all parameters. A vivid example is us, humans. If we were symmetric in every way and all had the exact same face, in the literal sense, the brain would be in a state of confusion. If all the planets, and everything in the universe, were symmetric, it would be a nightmare and horror for us. The brain would simply get tired of perfect forms everywhere.

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